

Determinants of the Implementation of Corporate Social Responsibility Programs Related to Higher Education: A Case Study in Northern Mexico

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to identify the main factors that motivate companies into investing in programs related to higher education, under the category of corporate social responsibility. This study utilizes a case study in a northern city in Mexico (i.e., Monterrey). In the preliminary results, eight factors have been identified, the first four are factors commonly mentioned in the previous literature (i.e., company size, mimicry, profitability, and sector), and the remaining four factors were found through qualitative analysis from interviews to relevant actors (personal networks of the administration or board, survival strategies, future employability competitiveness, and continuation of the founder's ideology).

Keywords: Corporate social responsibility, linkage industry – university, cross sectoral partnership, sustainability, mixed methods.

1. INTRODUCTION

This exploratory research aims to address the following research question: Why do companies decide to implement corporate social responsibility (CSR) programs related to higher education? To answer to this, the research is based on elucidating the main determinants in the implementation of CSR programs focused on higher education. A case study in a northern city in Mexico (i.e., Monterrey) is utilized to implement and test the proposed methodology.

This study expands previous studies by (1) Casalet and Casas (1998), which focuses on the determinants of the university-industry linkage exclusively from the perspective of the universities; (2) Carrillo, Layton and Tapia (2008), which focuses on 21 companies with investment of \$140 million Mexican pesos a year (£5.5 million pounds, approximately) in corporate social responsibility programs with education, childhood and health being the top three investments; and (3) Cardenas, Cabrero and Arellano (2012), which recognizes a structural weakness in the linkage process in Mexico, but without immersing in the dynamic aspects of these negotiations.

The relevance of Monterrey as an area of study comes in part from its relevance on the national scene, in terms of economic and educational developments. Monterrey is the 3rd largest metropolitan area of the country with

a population of close to 4.5 million people, it has 9.4% of the GDP while having 3% of the economical unities (INEGI, 2014), and it is the cradle of international companies as CEMEX, FEMSA, Grupo Alfa, Gamesa, Grupo Proeza and the brewery Cuauhtémoc Moctezuma, recently changed to Heineken Mexico (Martínez, 2012). With the advocacy of the founders of these companies, the initiative and investment for quality higher education institutions was born.

From the five biggest and most important universities in Monterrey and Mexico, four were created directly from private, company-related capital, and have stayed close to the private sector throughout their history: Tecnológico de Monterrey (ITESM), Universidad de Monterrey (UDEM), Universidad Regiomontana (Uerre) and Universidad Metropolitana de Monterrey (UMM) (Flores, 2009).

2. METHODOLOGY

A three-phase methodology has been proposed (refer to Figure 1). The methodology uses mixed methods, including semi-structured interviews, survey, and multifactorial analysis. This methodological design is sequential and the results obtained in one phase feed the next one.

The use of semi-structured interviews was chosen due to the nature of the information collected (i.e., matters

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related to experience and conversational reality from the relevant actors) (Brinkmann & Kvale, 2015).

Figure 1. Methodological design

2.1. Phase I: Universities

This phase consists of 9 interviews in 5 universities (i.e., 7 hrs. of audio and 120 pages of transcription, on average). The universities chosen are considered the most prominent in Monterrey in terms of their reputation, rankings, and size.

The audio material was transcribed, and subsequently analysed through coding using the specialized software MAXQDA (MAXQDA, 2017). From this material a list of companies that have linkage programs with these universities was created, and the 15 companies more involved with these universities were selected for the next step.

Additional information pertaining: (1) the main departments at these companies leading the linkage with universities (2) the duration of the programs, (3) the perspective of the university, its workers and student on these programs, and (4) common disagreements or challenges face by both parties in these interactions, was collected.

2.2 Phase II: Industry

Phase II consists of 12 interviews in 10 companies (i.e., 10 hours of audio and 220 pages of transcription in total). The companies interviewed were obtained from the 15 companies selected in the last phase.

Before approaching the companies, a brief overview of their financial and CSR, sustainability or philanthropy reports was conducted in order to determine fair comparison among companies in terms of size, profitability, number of employees, industry, city of creation, and the existence of company charitable foundations.

After the transcription and coding of the material obtained in phase II, 15 main categories and 49 subcategories were obtained. These included aspects such as (1) main actors in the decision making of the implementation of programs with universities, (2) the different labels under which companies administer social programs with universities (i.e., Corporate Social Responsibility, sustainability, charity, philanthropy, and less commonly, human resources), (3) the perceived benefits for the different actors involved, (4) the types of programs that are carried out, (5) the lack of regulation or manuals for the selection and implementation of these programs, (6) the company's process to select partnering universities, and (7) other relevant aspects of the partnership.

From this analysis, eight determinants were identified as relevant for the case study, four of which were previously mentioned in the literature review and four that were obtained through the interviews (Table 1).

Determinant	Source
Size	(Bansal, 2005); (Castelo & Lima, 2008); (Chih, Chih, & Chen, 2010); (Chivite, Enciso, Garcia, & Tua, 2014); (Gao, et al., 2005); (Pozniak, et al., 2011); and (Reverte, 2009)
Mimicry	(Bansal, 2005) (Castelo & Lima, 2008) (Reverte, 2009) (Bansal & Clelland, 2004), (Bansal & Roth, 2000) (Henriques & Sandorsky, 1996)
Profitability	(Bansal, 2005), (Castelo and Lima, 2008), (Chih et al., 2010), (Chivite et al., 2014), (Pozniak et al., 2011) and (Reverte, 2009)
Sector	(Chivite et al., 2014) and (Ranangen & Zobel, 2014)
Personal networks of the administration or board of directors.	Interviews
Survival strategy	Interviews
Future employability competitiveness	Interviews
Continuation of the founder's ideology	Interviews

Table 1. Main determinants

2.3 Phase III: Survey

Phase III consists of an online survey, based on the information obtained in the past two stages and the literature review. The online survey was sent to the database of two industry networks related to areas of CSR.

With the information obtained through the survey, a multivariate statistical analysis will be applied to find the determinant of the implementation of CSR programs in higher education. Results are expected to be obtained and analysed by the end of 2018.

3. PRELIMINARY CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

As part of an ongoing research project, this extended abstract presents the developments on the research of the determinants of the implementation of CSR programs, related to higher education, using the case of the city of Monterrey, Mexico.

So far, the research has obtained valuable information of the relevant factors that have an impact on the decision-making process of relevant actors in this cross-sectoral partnership.

Preliminary conclusions show that qualitative aspects might be more relevant to the implementation of these programs, including the investments that these usually carry, than the quantitative variable that have been studied previously.

The personal networks of the first line of administration or the board of directors and the continuation of the founder's ideology seem to be of the highest relevance when choosing partnering universities and the programs the company will participate in.

Other aspects like the lack of professionalization and accountability of these programs also draw attention to the real motivation and expected results from these interactions, leaving a fruitful line for future research.

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